

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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Lead partner: Q PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Authors: Leonidas Parodos, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

George Spyridopoulos, Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL

Reviewer: Arianna D'Addezio, APRE, Paola Zerilli, University of York

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
TABLE OF FIGURES.....	5
TABLE OF TABLES.....	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	6
1 INTRODUCTION	7
2 IPR MANAGEMENT OVERVIEW.....	8
2.1 OBJECTIVES	8
2.2 BACKGROUND	9
2.3 RESULTS.....	9
2.4 KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	9
2.5 ACCESS RIGHTS.....	9
2.6 PROTECTION OF RESULTS	10
2.6.1 TRADEMARKS AND SERVICE MARKS	11
2.6.2 PATENTS.....	11
2.6.3 UTILITY MODELS.....	12
2.6.4 COPYRIGHTS.....	12
2.6.5 TRADE SECRETS	13
2.6.6 CONFIDENTIALITY AGREEMENTS	13
3 IPR MANAGEMENT STRATEGY.....	15
3.1 START OF THE PROJECT	15
3.1.1 GRANT AGREEMENT	16
3.1.2 CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT.....	16
3.1.3 DEFINITION OF BACKGROUND	16
3.2 DURING PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION	17
3.2.1 BACKGROUND IDENTIFICATION	17
3.2.2 RESULTS IDENTIFICATION	17
3.2.3 OWNERSHIP OF RESULTS	17
3.2.4 PROTECTION OF RESULTS	18
3.2.5 EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS	19
3.2.6 DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS.....	19
3.3 POST PROJECT STAGE.....	20
3.4 ROLE OF THE EXPLOITATION MANAGER	20
3.5 KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT OF THE PROJECT	21

3.6	IP CONFLICTS	21
4	<u>IPR MATRIX METHODOLOGY</u>	<u>23</u>
4.1	IDENTIFICATION OF BACKGROUND	24
4.2	IDENTIFICATION OF PROJECT RESULTS	24
4.3	IDENTIFICATION OF KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	25
5	<u>MARINEWIND’S BACKGROUND, RESULTS AND KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS</u>	<u>27</u>
5.1	BACKGROUND	27
5.2	PROJECT RESULTS.....	28
5.3	KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS	37
6	<u>EXPLOITATION PLAN PER KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULT</u>	<u>39</u>
6.1	STAKEHOLDER DATABASE	39
6.2	MARINEWIND WEBGIS TOOL.....	40
6.3	BOOKLET ON MARINEWIND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	41
6.4	MARINEWIND REPLICABILITY PLAN	42
6.5	MARINEWIND BRAND AND COMMUNITY.....	43
7	<u>EXPLOITATION PLAN PER PARTNER</u>	<u>44</u>
8	<u>CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD</u>	<u>47</u>
9	<u>ANNEX 1 - QUESTIONNAIRE.....</u>	<u>48</u>

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: MARINEWIND IPR Management Stages.....	15
Figure 2: IPR Matrix Background	24
Figure 3: IPR Matrix Results.....	25
Figure 4: IPR Matrix Key Exploitable Results	25

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1: Access Rights.....	10
Table 2: Protection Instruments of Results	18
Table 3: Structure of IPR Matrix	23
Table 4: Background	27
Table 5: Results.....	28
Table 6: Key Exploitable Results	37
Table 7: Exploitation Plan for the Stakeholder Database.....	39
Table 8: Actions needed for the exploitation of the Stakeholder Database	40
Table 9: Exploitation Plan for the MARINEWIND webGIS tool.....	40
Table 10: Actions needed for the exploitation of the MARINEWIND webGIS tool.....	40
Table 11: Exploitation Plan for the Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations	41
Table 12: Actions needed for the exploitation of the Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations..	41
Table 13: Exploitation Plan for the MARINEWIND Replicability Plan.....	42
Table 14: Actions needed for the exploitation of the MARINEWIND Replicability Plan	42
Table 15: Exploitation Plan for the MARINEWIND brand and community	43
Table 16: Actions needed for the exploitation of the MARINEWIND brand and community.....	43
Table 17: Individual Exploitation Plans for partners	44

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Sound Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management is essential to enable the successful exploitation of MARINEWIND's Results. Therefore, the consortium of MARINEWIND places great emphasis in managing innovation and IPR in the framework of the project, with a view to effectively paving the way for the exploitation and sustainability of its results following its completion.

The current report presents the **initial version - Strategy** of MARINEWIND's **Strategic Exploitation Plan**, encompassing the project's Innovation and IPR Management Strategy. This document sheds light on the key terms and procedures pertaining to the management and protection of intellectual property, lays down the main components of the relevant methodology which will be adopted throughout the project (IPR Matrix methodology) and describes the initial results of its implementation, in terms of **Background IP, Results** and **Key Exploitable Results (KER)**.

Along these lines, an overview of MARINEWIND's Key Exploitable Results as envisioned at this stage of the project is presented, along with the partners' initial plans for their post-project exploitation. This report includes specific exploitation plans for each identified KER, including the target groups that stand to benefit from their use, as well as individual exploitation plans for each member of the MARINEWIND consortium.

The report will be elaborated and updated at the end of the project, when all the services of the project have been developed and validated. With that in mind, the final version of the Strategic Exploitation Plan will be developed on M36. This final version will specifically describe the project's KERs and their main exploitation routes, the target groups per project KER, the general terms of use of each KER and the relevant IPR provisions, the joint exploitation plans for the consortium as well as per individual project partner (or groups of partners), the means and procedures for the exploitation of the KERs and a roadmap to this end.

1 INTRODUCTION

The MARINEWIND partners are committed to producing results that will be sustainable after the project's completion, all while ensuring that innovative ideas emerging from the project are fully investigated in terms of exploitation potential. To this end, MARINEWIND places great emphasis not only on managing the **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)** of the partners' ideas and project results, but also on mapping out the expected uses and benefits of each MARINEWIND Key Exploitable Result (KER), with a view to effectively paving the way for smooth exploitation and sustainability of its results, following the completion of the project.

With that in mind, the current document represents the **initial version** of the MARINEWIND **Strategic Exploitation Plan - Strategy** which will serve as the basis for the activities to be carried out in the framework of Task 5.4 towards sound innovation management as well as towards exploitation and sustainability of the project's results after the end of the grant.

This initial version of MARINEWIND Strategic Exploitation Plan – Strategy comprises 8 chapters, as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the context in which this report has been elaborated, its relation to other project activities, as well as to its structure.
- **Chapter 2** clarifies key terms pertaining to IPR management, defines the underlying objectives in the framework of the project and offers an overview of intellectual property protection instruments that could be employed.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the Innovation and IPR management strategy and its underlying stages in the context of MARINEWIND and describes the methodology to be adopted in this respect.
- **Chapter 4** introduces the IPR Matrix and explains the procedures followed to identify the MARINEWIND background IP and Results as well as the project's key exploitable results, as perceived at this stage of the project.
- **Chapter 5** offers a preliminary overview of the background IP and Results of project partners and the project's key exploitable results, as identified at this stage of the project.
- **Chapter 6** describes the exploitation plans per project KER, including actions that are currently foreseen as necessary for the KERs to be exploited.
- **Chapter 7** outlines the individual exploitation plan set out by each of the members of the MARINEWIND consortium at this stage of the project.
- **Chapter 8** concludes on the next steps foreseen in the context of the project towards the exploitation of its Key Exploitable Results.

The MARINEWIND Strategic Exploitation Plan – Strategy will be updated and further elaborated, according to the project's progress. More specific, its updated and **final version** is expected at **the end of the project (M36)** and will include the final description and owners of the project's Key Exploitable Results as well as their plans regarding IP protection and valorization, which are expected to facilitate exploitation after the end of the project.

2 IPR MANAGEMENT OVERVIEW

The following subsections aim to set the objectives of the IPR management strategy as well as to clarify the main terms concerning the key elements of IPR management, which represent the principal aspects of the IPR management procedures of the project.

2.1 Objectives

MARINEWIND's IPR management objectives embrace the need to protect project's KERs in order to handle and manage efficiently all the outcomes that will stem during the project's life span with a view to ensuring the exploitation and dissemination of MARINEWIND's Key Exploitable Results. To this end, the main objectives of the MARINEWIND's Innovation and IPR Management Strategy are the following:

- Define and describe the IPR management methodology to be followed within the context of MARINEWIND during the project.
- Identify the Results that will emerge from the activities foreseen within the lifecycle of the project thus determining a Results' portfolio from the initial stages of the project.
- Develop a collective understanding among MARINEWIND's partners, concerning key terms and issues revolving around the background IP and Results and respective access rights.
- Assess and conceptualize a preliminary framework of the IP protection that will be employed for each identified key exploitable result of MARINEWIND.
- Monitor, identify and eventually resolve any conflicts that may arise in terms of IP within the consortium and beyond if applicable.
- Establish common guiding routes and actions within the consortium to safeguard the smooth operation of the IPR strategies to be implemented.

In general, the key concepts to consider for designing the Innovation and IPR management strategy of Horizon Europe projects are the following¹:

- Background
- Results
- Key Exploitable Results
- Dissemination
- Access rights

Therefore, the following subsections aim to clarify the main terms concerning the key elements of IPR management, which represent key aspects of the IPR management procedures of the project.

¹ European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, [Your guide to Intellectual Property Management in Horizon Europe](#), Publications Office, 2022

2.2 Background

Background IP means any **data expertise or information** – whatever is form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that is:

- Held by the partners before they acceded to the Agreement and
- Needed to implement the action or exploit the results.

If background is subject to rights of a third party, the beneficiary concerned must ensure that it is able to comply with its obligations under the Agreement².

2.3 Results

By the term Results, any tangible or intangible output of the project is meant, such as data, knowledge, or information, which is generated in the project, whatever its form or nature, whether or not it can be protected, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights³. In this respect, project Results can arise and be obtained from project partners to protect and exploit the underlying Key Exploitable Results of the project which include intellectual property rights (e.g., copyrights, industrial designs, patents). It should be noted that results generated outside the project activities cannot be defined as project results.

2.4 Key Exploitable Results

Exploitation of project's results means the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities⁴.

Under this scheme, A Key Exploitable Result (KER) is an identified main interesting result (either the whole result or a part of it) or a combination of results, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education⁵. To this end, not all project results may meet the above conditions and be identified as Key Exploitable Results.

2.5 Access Rights

Access rights refer to user rights for requesting access to a project partner's background and results in order to implement its activities under the project or to use its own results. In addition, access rights can be utilized as long as they are needed for exploiting the project's results. The granting of access

² See Article 16.1 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

³ See Article 16.2 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

⁴ See Annex 5 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

⁵ HEU Results Platform, [Introducing the Horizon Results Platform and Horizon Results Platform TV](#)

rights within a collaborative Horizon Europe project follows specific rules pre-defined in the Grant Agreement⁶ and the Consortium Agreement⁷. Depending on their purpose of use, access rights within MARINEWIND are depicted in the following table.

Table 1: Access Rights

Purpose for Access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Project implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royalty-free Unless otherwise agreed in Attachment 1 of Consortium Agreement 	Royalty-free
Exploitation of Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Access rights to results for internal research and for teaching activities on a royalty free basis. Fair and reasonable conditions A request for Access Rights may be made up to six months after the end of the Project or after the termination of the requesting Party's participation in the Project. 	

2.6 Protection of Results

Protection of Results constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale, or commercialization of IP in the form of products and services. Moreover, its utilization is vital for prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it can contribute to support the branding of products and services both to customers and investors.

When considering IP protection, it must be noted that IP results can be protected by several types of IPR, and consequently, the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The selection of the most suitable form of IP protection depends on the nature and specific characteristics of the results under consideration and the objectives of the IP owner.

There are various types of instruments that may be considered for protecting IP. Under the frame of MARINEWIND, meaningful IP protection instruments that can be used are the following:

- Trade and service marks
- Patents
- Utility models
- Copyrights
- Trade secrets
- Confidentiality agreements

⁶ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

⁷ See Section 9 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement

Further details with respect to each of the above-mentioned protection instruments are provided in the subsections below.

2.6.1 Trademarks and service marks

Trademarks

A trademark constitutes an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered⁸. Trademarks consist of signs capable of distinguishing the products (either goods or services) of a trader from those of others. The main function of a trademark is to identify the commercial origin of a product. This does not mean that it must inform the consumer of the actual person who has manufactured the product or even the one who is trading in it. It is sufficient that the consumer can trust in each enterprise, not necessarily known to him, being responsible for the product sold under the trademark.

Service Marks

In modern trade, consumers are offered not only a vast choice of goods of all kinds but also with an increasing variety of services which tend increasingly to be offered on a national and even international scale. There is therefore also a need for signs that enable the consumers to distinguish between the different services such as insurance companies, car rental firms, airlines, etc.

These signs are called service marks and fulfil the same origin-indicating and distinguishing function for services as trademarks do for goods. Since service marks are signs that are similar in nature to trademarks, the same criteria can be applied. Thus, service mark protection has sometimes been introduced by a short amendment to the existing trademark law, simply providing for the application to service marks of the provisions on the protection of trademarks⁹.

2.6.2 Patents

A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) offering a new technical solution or facilitating a new way of doing something. The patent holder enjoys the exclusive right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting their invention for a limited period. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application¹⁰.

A patent does not give its owner the positive right to use the patented invention. Third party rights may have to be requested. Still, a patent owner has the right to decide who may or may not use the patented invention throughout the period during which the invention is protected. Moreover, the patent owner may give permission to other parties, or license them, to use the invention on mutually

⁸ European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, [Your guide to IP in Europe, Publication Office](#), 2019, p.5

⁹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 68

¹⁰ See [Your Guide to IP in Europe](#) for the definition of patents in the European context

agreed terms. The owner may also sell the right to the invention to someone, who then becomes the new owner of the patent. Finally, patents are granted only country by country, some regionally, and may also be used in non-patented territories.

Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and the invention becomes part of the public domain, in the sense that the owner no longer holds exclusive rights in it, and it becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others¹¹.

2.6.3 Utility Models

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorization, for a limited period¹². The inclusion of utility models into the intellectual property system in some countries has the primary objective of nurturing the rapid evolution of indigenous innovativeness, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises and among individuals¹³.

2.6.4 Copyrights

Copyright (or author’s right) is the term used to describe the rights that creators have over their literary, scientific, and artistic works. There is not an exhaustive list containing the works that can be protected by copyright. However, several pieces of work are usually covered by copyright at international level¹⁴:

- Literary works such as novels, poems, plays, newspaper
- articles
- computer programs, databases
- films, musical compositions, and choreographies
- artistic works such as paintings, drawings, photographs
- sculptures
- architecture, and
- advertisements, maps, and technical drawings

Copyright protection also includes moral rights, including the right to claim authorship of a work, and the right to oppose changes to it that could harm the creator's reputation. The creator - or the owner of the copyright in a work - can enforce rights administratively and in the courts, by inspection of premises for evidence of production or possession of illegally made “pirated” goods related to

¹¹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 17

¹² Definition of utility models in the European context retrieved from [Your Guide to IP in Europe](#)

¹³ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40

¹⁴ European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, [Your guide to IP in Europe](#), Publications Office, 2019, p.33

protecting works. The owner may obtain court orders to stop such activities, as well as seek damages for loss of financial rewards and recognition. Finally, it is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original¹⁵.

A very common and useful copyright tool that is applied is the **Creative Commons License (CC)**, which forge a balance inside the traditional “all rights reserved” setting that copyright law creates. These copyright licenses and tools give everyone from individual creators to large companies and institutions a simple, standardized way to grant copyright permissions to their creative work. There are several Creative Commons Licenses and each one helps the creators retain copyright while allowing others to copy, distribute, and make some uses of their work, at least non-commercially. Furthermore, every Creative Commons license ensures creators get the credit for their work they deserve, and also works around the world and lasts as long as applicable copyright lasts (because they are built on copyright). The set of Creative Commons licenses is composed of the following licenses¹⁶:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

2.6.5 Trade Secrets

Any confidential business information providing a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. The type of information that can be protected as a trade secret is therefore highly diverse. It can include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes or manufacturing processes¹⁷.

2.6.6 Confidentiality Agreements

Confidentiality is an extremely critical issue for participants in innovation projects, from the setting-up to the implementation and exploitation phases. Exchanging valuable information with other partners is a necessity that regularly occurs in collaborative initiatives or undertakings. Accordingly, confidentiality issues and measures should be taken into consideration to safely exchange information, facilitating the project development, and ensuring the non-disclosure of sensitive technology, business or commercially confidential information. Confidentiality agreements provide protection and more

¹⁵ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40

¹⁶ For more information about Creative Commons licenses visit: [CreativeCommons.org](https://creativecommons.org)

¹⁷ European Commission, Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises, [Your guide to IP in Europe](#), Publications Office, 2019, p.29

security to an organisation that is about to share or make available information to another organisation by ensuring that confidential information will be used only for the permitted purposes agreed between the signatories of the agreement and will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent. Therefore, the signature of a confidentiality agreement can be seen as a very important step to keep confidential information secret in order to maintain a competitive edge¹⁸.

¹⁸ See Non-Disclosure Agreement of European IPR Helpdesk: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-03/One-Way-Non-Disclosure-Agreement-EN-1_2021.pdf

3 IPR MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

Under the frame of MARINEWIND, key IP and innovation management will be employed, with a view to setting a common understanding concerning the background, results, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, dissemination and exploitation during and after the project development. In this respect, the MARINEWIND IPR management strategy applies a comprehensive framework which separates the IP management processes of the project in the following stages:

- Start of the Project
- During Project Implementation
- After Project End

In this respect, the following figure illustrates the IPR management stages, as considered within MARINEWIND. More details about these stages are shown below.

Figure 1: MARINEWIND IPR Management Stages

3.1 Start of the Project

Both the **Grant Agreement** and the **Consortium Agreement** constitute documents which include a **description of several issues related to IPR**. Their unique provisions represent a reference point for IPR issues within the project partners. In this respect, any further advancements regarding IPR actions to be put in place by project partners will be facilitated under the underlying provisions.

3.1.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement constitutes a contract which sets out the key rules and conditions of the project and is conducted between the EC and the MARINEWIND partners. It represents the main contractual basis for MARINEWIND while its main points and sections referring to IPR are included in **Section 2 “Specific Rules for carrying out the Action”**¹⁹. Under this scheme, the management of the MARINEWIND IP is regulated, whereas access rights and obligations related to the background are set. In addition, the GA defines issues concerning the ownership and protection of the project’s generated results, as well as their exploitation and dissemination. Finally, transferability and access rights to results are also defined in the MARINEWIND GA.

3.1.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement constitutes a contract among the partners of MARINEWIND consortium which aims to define rights and obligations within the partnership for the purposes of conducting the project’s foreseen actions and activities²⁰. The CA minimizes the probability of later disputes as it provides rules and responsibilities during the project as well as defines the access rights to be granted to the partners concerning the project. In addition, rights and responsibilities are outlined among the consortium members concerning issues of the IP.

The MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement main points and sections referring to IPR are contained in:

- **Section 8 “Results”**, that sets out provisions on ownership and joint ownership of results, as well as on their transfer and dissemination.
- **Section 9 “Access Rights”**, which clarifies the access rights governing principles along with the access rights for the exploitation and dissemination purposes. It also states specific provisions for access rights to the software.
- **Attachment 1 “Background included”** that presents the initial list of usable background IP.

3.1.3 Definition of Background

At the start of the project, all project partners must identify the background that is pertinent for the project actions and grant access rights to this IP, in principle²¹. The background of a project can be identified and agreed within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, considering two main aspects:

- **Identification of background:** Naming of the background IP that each project partner provides to the consortium, and which are imperative for successful implementation and exploitation of the project actions.

¹⁹ See Article 18 and Annex 5 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

²⁰ See Section 2 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement

²¹ See Attachment 1 in the Consortium Agreement for a detailed description of the MARINEWIND background and the access rights granted in principle for the consortium.

- **Definition of Access Rights:** Clarification of the rights to use knowledge under the terms and conditions agreed within the consortium and in align with the underlying background rules and obligations set by the EC in order to ensure the smooth implementation of the project.

3.2 During Project Implementation

During the implementation stage of the project, IP handling procedures are foreseen to be applied among the MARINEWIND partners to properly organize results management of the project. In this respect, as the project evolves, the focus will be on project results identification, ownership, access rights, and protection of results, as well as exploitation. MARINEWIND IPR management emphasizes the establishment of robust handling procedures of IPR issues that are of strategic importance to the project to facilitate exploitation of its results.

Therefore, partners should focus on two different points:

- **Providing access rights to their knowledge** for other partners to carry out their work on the project.
- **Establishing early result identification procedures** with a view to protecting, disseminating, and exploiting the project's key exploitable results, all while fostering long-term cooperation among partners and efficient project management.

In this respect, key IP related issues in the MARINEWIND implementation phase include:

3.2.1 Background identification

During the project implementation stage, it is imperative to identify the relevant Background items, if any, complementary to those outlined in the Consortium Agreement. To this end, any partner may add additional Background to Attachment 1 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement during the project, provided they give written notice to other partners. However, in case that a partner wishes to modify or withdraw its Background in Attachment 1, approval of the General Assembly will be needed according to the Consortium Agreement provisions²².

3.2.2 Results identification

A core process of the MARINEWIND IP management is the project results' identification with a view to creating a concrete mapping of the project's results and enhancing the MARINEWIND IP portfolio. Therefore, all valuable IP within the project must be identified, listed, named, described and analyzed in a systematic way.

3.2.3 Ownership of Results

The Grant Agreement of MARINEWIND establishes that the results of the project are owned by the partner(s) that generates them. Given the collaborative nature of the project, an individual result can be jointly developed by two or more partners and its joint ownership is subject to the agreement on

²² See Section 9 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement

the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership²³. Although regulations concerning the frame of joint ownership are embedded in the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement²⁴, partners may establish during the project implementation a separate joint ownership agreement in order to define the allocation and terms of exercising their ownership.

Moreover, according to the [Europe Horizon reporting template](#), MARINEWIND partners are requested to prepare a **Results Ownership List** to clarify ownership of project results and to facilitate the process for exploitation of these by project partners and, where relevant, third parties. As a minimum, the list should include details of whether the result has single or joint ownership, the name of the owner(s), the country of establishment of the owner(s) and whether the results will be exploited by the owner(s). The Results Ownership List will be prepared and included in the final version of Exploitation Plan as well as in the **Final Periodic Report**, where the ownership of projects results will be fully defined amongst MARINEWIND partners.

For the initial version of Exploitation Plan, partners gave their contribution through a Questionnaire (Annex I) based on the IPR Matrix (See IPR Matrix Methodology in Section 4) to elaborate further on the provisions of the CA with regards to results' ownership.

3.2.4 Protection of Results

Effective exploitation of the innovative concepts and KERs developed under the frame of MARINEWIND depends on the protection of the project's results. Consortium partners are bound by the terms of their grants and must adequately protect their results, for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage, if²⁵:

- The project's results can be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited and,
- Protecting them is possible and justified (given the circumstances)

In this respect, when considering IP protection MARINEWIND partners must consider their own legitimate interests, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, along with the legitimate interests of the whole consortium and any other legitimate interests. The table that follows illustrates the different protection instruments that can be applied to a variety of subjects.

Table 2: Protection Instruments of Results

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility Model	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Invention	X	X			X
Software	X*	X	X		X
Scientific Article			X		
Technology Design			X	X	

²³ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

²⁴ See Paragraph 8.2 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement

²⁵ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

Name of Technology				X	
Know How	X	X			X
Website			X	X	X
*Software patentability is still a debated issue given its exclusion as subject matter as by Article 52(2)(c) and (3) of the European Patent Convention (EPC). Source: IPR Helpdesk .					

3.2.5 Exploitation of Results

The identified Key Exploitable Results of MARINEWIND will be exploited as foreseen within the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement²⁶. Particularly, consortium partners should be fully aware that they must, up to four years after project completion, use their best efforts to ensure exploitation of their results, either directly or indirectly by another entity, through transfer or licensing.

If, despite the best effort for exploitation, no uptake happens within the following year after the end of the project, the partners must use the [Horizon Results Platform](#) to make exploitable results visible to potential interested entities, unless obligation is waived, which is free and part of the [Funding & Tenders Portal](#).

To this end, the MARINEWIND consortium will seek exploitation opportunities of the project's results in (i) further research activities (outside the action), (ii) developing, creating or marketing a product or process, (iii) creating and providing a service, (iv) using them in standardization activities or other use scenarios such as to inform policy or for educational purposes. Hence, exploitation is by no means limited to commercial exploitation²⁷.

In parallel to the successive phases of IP identification, determination of claims for ownership and exploitation as well as the definition of IP protection measures, further actions will run, including:

- Outlining of potential exploitation routes anticipated for each of MARINEWIND's KERs beyond the end of the project.
- Elaboration of the MARINEWIND Exploitation Plan to serve as the road map for the roll-out of the exploitable results of the project after the end of the Grant.

3.2.6 Dissemination of Results

MARINEWIND partners are set to select the appropriate means for dissemination of project results (e.g., scientific publications, publication on web sites, conferences, etc.), according to the conditions set forth in the CA and in other specific confidentiality agreements that might arise in order to maintain confidentiality during and after the end of the project²⁸. Additionally, partners must disseminate their

²⁶ See Article 16 and Annex 5 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

²⁷ European Commission, [Your guide to IP management in Horizon Europe](#), p.20

²⁸ See Paragraph 8.4 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement

results as soon as they are feasible by using publicly available formats in accordance with any restrictions due to IP protection, security rules or legitimate interests and the provisions of GA²⁹.

Along with that, the Open Science approach will be followed by partners, which focuses on spreading knowledge as soon as it is available using digital and collaborative technology. Considering that, MARINEWIND partners have been invited to make their scientific publications available as Open Access publications, and grant access as open as possible and as closed as necessary³⁰.

It must be noted that all partners should be aware that they first ensure the protection of a project's exploitable result and then proceed to dissemination actions of this or any other underlying result.

3.3 Post Project Stage

At the project's conclusion, the final version of the Strategic Exploitation Plan will be submitted, outlining the use that MARINEWIND consortium intends to make of its Key Exploitable Results and the related plans and time frame for their exploitation. The plan will describe the further activities that need to be implemented to ensure the use and long-term sustainability of MARINEWIND Key Exploitable Results. In addition, it will include the final findings concerning IP issues, as well as the final update of the IPR Matrix (See Section 4), detailing the intellectual property rights applied and registered. This deliverable, therefore, will envisage the final strategy of the consortium as shaped at the end of the project for exploitation, management of intellectual property rights and sustainability, including also any selected commercialization pathways if applicable.

At this final stage of the project, consortium partners will employ some basic actions, aiming to ensure the sound post-project management of the innovation and exploitation processes. Typically, they will:

- Explore exploitation strategies and pathways, either joint or not, and agree on the most suitable ones.
- Look at IP ownership arrangements and related responsibilities, including the definition of relative contributions of joint-owners, and
- Weigh potential (licensing) agreement and remuneration options linked to the use of IP resulting from the project and options for remuneration.

On the other hand, there will be follow-up by the EC on partners' progress, needs and obstacles on their path towards exploitation two years after the end of the project. Under this frame, MARINEWIND partners will be called to complete a structured Questionnaire to report on their exploitation state.

3.4 Role of the Exploitation Manager

The Exploitation Manager (EM) is responsible for defining the project's Innovation and IPR Management Strategy, preparing the respective reports and ensuring that innovative ideas which arise during the project will be thoroughly examined and assessed for potential exploitation, while at the

²⁹ See Article 17 and Annex 5 of the MARINEWIND Grant Agreement

³⁰ European Commission, [Your guide to IP management in Horizon Europe](#), p.19

same time all background intellectual property and results of the project is managed. To this end, the EM will be in close communication with the Project Coordinator and the General Assembly to ensure continuous feedback from escalating project activities from the start until the project completion.

The Exploitation Manager will be responsible for the organisation and management issues of the MARINEWIND IPR strategy implementation. It is considered good practice for a partner to inform and consult the EM accordingly before deciding whether to protect the results stemming from its underlying activities or not – particularly if the partner is considering a potential joint IP scheme.

Finally, the EM also assumes a mediation role in case of IP conflicts (see Section 3.6), monitors project activities and feeds the development of the subsequent versions of this report.

3.5 Knowledge Management of the Project

The management of the IP constitutes an integral part of the overall MARINEWIND project management structure and thus it is important to establish a permanent IP monitoring scheme during the project. In this respect, an efficient IPR management methodology should define, from the early stages of the project, the procedures under which newly generated/ identified results will be handled within the lifespan of MARINEWIND.

Efficient management of IP in MARINEWIND will be achieved through adopting a process able to identify IP results as well as to determine their adequate handling and protection. In this respect, it is essential to establish mechanisms that will guarantee that IP information is dependable and timely captured. Should WP Leaders identify a new result that will be generated under their respective WP activities, the Exploitation Manager must be informed accordingly.

The MARINEWIND EM constitutes the party that will organize the screening and the management of any newly identified results and their corresponding IP issues that arise during the project's lifespan. The EM will direct the consortium partners to establish the most adequate and efficient IPR strategy based on the nature of the newly identified result and the purposes of the MARINEWIND consortium concerning the exploitation of this result. To facilitate this process, the MARINEWIND IPR management strategy foresees creating and updating a living IPR Matrix (See section 4) to be revised and extended with new pieces of project results as the project's implementation advances.

3.6 IP Conflicts

To proactively avoid IP conflicts, project partners will be well-informed about IP rules and guided through the exploitation process with the help of the EM and the IPR Matrix. In this respect, partners will identify their IPR results, formulate their ownership and exploitation claims and if deemed necessary, transfer any relevant results to MARINEWIND's key exploitable results according to the principal rights and obligations defined in the Consortium Agreement of MARINEWIND (Section 8 of MARINEWIND CA). The Exploitation Manager will provide assistance for the following indicative (and not exclusive) issues:

- Is there a possible misunderstanding about the definition of the exploitable result and therefore of the object of claims?

- Are there exploitation claims that should be further specified so that the partners can check the compatibility of their claims?
- Are the foreseen exploitation claims compatible with the ownership claims of the partners (related issue of access rights)?
- Are there any confidentiality issues e.g., new knowledge of strategic importance for a partner and consequently the need for a confidential agreement?
- Are there any possible IP conflicts between the partners, both related to ownership and the related need for access rights and to exploitation claims?

In terms of IP conflict, the Exploitation Manager will encourage conflicting parties to get in contact and proactively find solutions, making written agreements whenever necessary. In case no agreement is achieved, the internal mediation process will be kicked off following the provisions of section 11.8 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement. In case the IP issues remain unresolved after this first mediation procedure, further mediation processes will be applied according to the MARINEWIND CA provisions (See Section 11.8 of the MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement).

4 IPR MATRIX METHODOLOGY

The MARINEWIND IPR management approach foresees the utilization of an IPR Matrix to define the main IPR issues concerning the MARINEWIND Innovation and IPR Management Strategy. This approach will support all partners in identifying and managing the background knowledge, the results and key exploitable results of the project in order to have a full overview about IP protection and necessary agreements to enable successful exploitation.

The IPR Matrix methodology is comprised of 4 distinct but interconnected steps, as follows:

- **Step 1:** Addition of new Background and definition of access rights among partners within the project according to the CA processes³¹, complementary to the identified BG³² in the MARINEWIND CA at the start of the project.
- **Step 2:** Identification of the planned results under the MARINEWIND activities.
- **Step 3:** Identification of the project's key exploitable results (as defined at this early stage of the project) and the **partners contributing** to each one along with their corresponding interest for their exploitation.
- **Step 4:** Definition of a preliminary framework of IPR protection for the defined MARINEWIND results, which will enhance their further exploitation.

At this early stage of the project, the objective of the Strategic Exploitation Plan of MARINEWIND is to define the Key Exploitable Results on the one hand and identify, to the extent possible, the BG and results of the project along with their corresponding access rights on the other hand. During the later stages of the project's implementation, the Strategic Exploitation Plan will be updated accordingly, in order to capture and integrate the evolvement of the identified results and IPR approach of the project. In particular, the identification of KER would yield the need to establish an ownership regime among project partners for each one of the KER. In addition, rules and conditions to get access to KER need also to be considered. Finally, the selection of the IPR to be employed in each case will follow.

Under this framework, the structure of the IPR Matrix that will be used throughout the duration of the project is summarized below.

Table 3: Structure of IPR Matrix

Background (BG)	Results (R)	Key Exploitable Results (KER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BG# • Partner's Background • Short description of BG • Type of protection • Conditions to use within MARINEWIND. • Conditions to use outside MARINEWIND. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R# • Project Result • Related WP • Contributing partners • Short description of R • Related BG# • Type of protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KER# • Key Exploitable Result • Main partner • Further contributing partner(s) • Related R# • Related BG#

³¹ See Paragraph 9.1.2 of MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement.

³² See Attachment 1 of MARINEWIND Consortium Agreement.

WP	#	Project result (R)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	Short description of FG	R number	Type of protection	Conditions to use within MARINEWIND	Interest in Further Exploitation of Project Results	Conditions to use after the end of project

Figure 3: IPR Matrix Results

In the first four columns, the MARINEWIND results along with the relevant WP, are listed. In the fifth column, the main partner responsible for the Results shall be indicated. In the sixth column, the further contributing partners for the Results shall be indicated as well. In the seventh column, the related background number is attached to the underlying R. In the eighth column, a short text describing the identified R shall be included by the responsible partner. In the ninth column, an R number shall be attached to each result per contributing partner. In the tenth column, partners shall indicate relevant IP protection type(s) for the R (e.g., patent, copyright, etc.). In the next column, the conditions to use the R within MARINEWIND (e.g., free to use or subject to charges) shall be indicated by each partner whether there are any restrictions to use the R or not. In the twelfth column, the project partners shall describe if they have an interest in exploitation of the project result. Finally, in the last column, the conditions (e.g., free to use, license fee, etc.) to use after the project shall be indicated by the partners.

4.3 Identification of Key Exploitable Results

Based on the identified Results the partners will define their key exploitable results along with the underlying IPR provisions, such as protection, definition of access rights and exploitation pathways.

At this step, the third part of the IPR Matrix was elaborated, which defined the Key Exploitable Results (KER), indicating the main contributors for these results, with the aims:

- To **identify IP ownership and exploitation claims**, as well as pro-actively indicate possible conflicts for each exploitable result; and
- To **support decisions on issues pertaining to IP protection**, in order to timely take the needed steps in this regard, including any potential IP agreements (e.g., for joint ownership, providing access rights or even an NDA for confidentiality).

The following figure provides an illustrative overview of this part of the IPR Matrix.

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Short description of KER	Main partner(s)	Contributing Partner(s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)

Figure 4: IPR Matrix Key Exploitable Results

In the first two columns, the number and a short name of the identified exploitable results are listed. In the third column, a short text of the identified KER shall be included. In the following column, the main partner(s) responsible for the KER shall be listed. In the fifth column, other relevant contributing partner(s) for the KER shall be indicated as well. In the sixth column, the related R number shall be indicated, whereas in the seventh column the relevant background number shall be stated. In the eighth column, a proposition of the IP ownership of the KER shall be indicated by the main partner contributing to the creation of the KER. In the next column, the responsible partner shall indicate the relevance for possible IP protection. In the next 5 columns, the exploitation routes are divided into five different categories:

- M: Making a product and selling it.
- U: Using the project result internally for further development, for instance:
 - to develop something else for sale; or
 - for R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research projects.
- L: Licensing the project result to third parties.
- S: Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc.
- O: Others

The responsible partner for the KER shall choose which exploitation routes are appropriate in consultation with the contributing partners, the Project Coordinator and the Exploitation Manager. Finally, in the last column, the responsible partner shall indicate which exploitation route would be the most promising.

5 MARINEWIND’S BACKGROUND, RESULTS AND KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

5.1 Background

The Background as preliminary identified in the CA preparation and further elaborated according to the MARINEWIND CA processes to be used so as to achieve the objectives of MARINEWIND is presented in the following table.

Table 4: Background

#	Relevant Background	Contributing Partner	BG number	Short description of BG	Type of protection	Conditions to use within MARINEWIND	Conditions to use outside MARINEWIND	Interest in further exploitation through MARINEWIND's results	Remarks
1	Know-how in developing webGIS tools	RSE	BG 1	Know-how in using the open-source framework Terria JS (TerriaMap) for developing WebGIS tools	Know how	Will be used for project's activities by RSE	Will be used for project's activities by RSE		

5.2 Project Results

Table 5: Results

WP	#	Project result (R)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	Short description of FG	R number	Type of protection	Conditions to use within MARINEWIND	Interest in Further Exploitation of Project Results	Conditions to use after the end of project
1	1.1	Analysis of policy and regulatory barriers and enablers to floating offshore wind deployment	Assessment of main barriers and bottlenecks of the consenting process at Lab level	CNR	RSE, ESC, Sener, YoY, WavEC, ELE		Identification of the main barriers and bottlenecks of the consenting process to assess the implications of the legal framework and the authorization steps at Lab level	R 1.1.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
			Assessment of Offshore wind Support Policies	ESC	RSE, CNR, Sener, YoY, WavEC, ELE		An assessment of the current renewable support policies in Labs that have enabled the growth of offshore wind, the impact of the framework on the electricity market, key barriers and opportunities for financing and innovation development and priorities for a coherent electricity market design reform for the near, medium and longer-term	R 1.1.2	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

			Lab profiles on current and future Energy Market conditions	RSE	ESC, CNR, Sener, YoY, WavEC, ELE	The consortium will develop Lab profiles defining current and future market conditions including carbon policy and market design, public and private financing, and the implications of a power mix for future energy market design and policy framework	R 1.1.3	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
1	1.2	Creation of a stakeholders database	Stakeholders database	APRE	All Partners	A database with relevant stakeholders at Labs and European level and their level of influence in the system	R 1.2.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
1	1.3	Organization of Labs co-creation activities	Co-created knowledge	APRE	All Partners	New knowledge co-created through a permanent dialogue with and among the MARINEWIND Quintuple Helix stakeholders during co-creation workshops	R 1.3.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

1	1.4	Elaboration of results of policy analysis	Policy analysis	ESC	All Partners	An analysis on the key firm, regional and country characteristics, the individual variables' comparative importance, the impact of policy and regulatory barriers and enablers on the development of FOWT technologies and on the performance of innovative firms who develop such technologies	R 1.4.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
2	2.1	Analysis of social and environmental barriers and enablers	Social barriers and enablers	SENER	APRE, UoY, ESC, WavEC, CNR, RSE, Q-PLAN, EP	Content for driving co-creation activities that will involve local communities in the Labs	R 2.1.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
			Environmental barriers and enablers	CNR	APRE, UoY, ESC, WavEC, Sener, RSE, Q-PLAN, EP	The environmental analysis represents one of the fundamental steps to obtain authorizations for offshore wind farm installation	R 2.1.2	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
2	2.2	Identification of conflict management solutions	Conflict management solutions	SENER	APRE, UoY, ESC, WavEC, CNR, RSE, Q-PLAN, EP	A set of possible solutions to reduce conflicts between offshore wind renewable energy installations and other activities at sea	R 2.2.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

2	2.3	Elaboration of results of social and environmental analysis	Social and environmental analysis	RSE	UoY, SENER, CNR, Q-PLAN	An analysis of the characteristics affecting the environmental impact of FOWT and the social acceptance related to FOWT and of the influence of this impact to the development of FOWT	R 2.3.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
3	3.1	Analysis of financial and market barriers and enablers	Initial Analysis of financial and market barriers and enablers	UoY	WAVEC, ESC, RSE, CNR, ELE	Analysis on barriers and enablers to Public Private Partnerships (PPPs), Green Public Procurement (GPP), Other possible innovative financial schemes, Involvement of innovative SMEs and Circular Economy	R 3.1.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
			Market analysis of the MARINEWIND Labs	WavEC	UoY, ESC, RSE, CNR, ELE	Analysis to identify challenges, opportunities, risks, barriers and enablers to FOWT commercialization	R 3.1.2	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
			Cost-Benefit analysis	UoY	WAVEC, ESC, RSE, CNR, ELE	Sensitivity analysis to estimate the Levelized Cost Of Energy (LCOE, ratio between the sum of costs over lifetime and the sum of electrical energy produced over lifetime)	R 3.1.3	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

			Financing Solutions	UoY	WAVEC, ESC, RSE, CNR, ELE		Financing solutions to facilitate investment in FOWT	R 3.1.4	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
3	3.2	Analysis of technological barriers and enablers and data collection	Initial analysis of the technological barriers	CNR	WavEC, SENER, RSE, ESC, ELE		An analysis of the current technological barriers as well as those arising with the novel frontier of FOWT technology and their correlation with geographical characteristics, climate changes, circular economy and impact on marine ecosystems	R 3.2.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
			Hybrid technologies	RSE	WavEC, SENER, CNR, ESC, ELE		Analysis of pros and cons, challenges and replicability issues of the combination of FOWT with wave and tidal devices, floating PV and hydrogen production	R 3.2.2	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
			System requirements, flexibility and integration	ESC	WavEC, SENER, RSE, CNR, ELE		An analysis on how to meet the optimal requirements (storage, flexibility, integration, etc.) and on present challenges and future market opportunities	R 3.2.3	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

D5.7: Strategic Exploitation Plan - Strategy

			Technological analysis of the MARINEWIND labs	CNR	WavEC, SENER, RSE, ESC, ELE		An analysis on technological issues depending on the geographical area of each Lab	R 3.2.4	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
4	4.1	Development of the MARINEWIND webGIS tool	MARINEWIND webGIS tool	RSE	All Partners		A web multifunctional tool that will provide the stakeholders with information, best practices, financing solutions, guidelines and impact assessments	R 4.1.1	Not applicable Open tool	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
4	4.2	Recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders	Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations	Q-PLAN	All Partners		Recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders at European and Labs level to ensure the valorization of the activities and results coming from the Labs	R 4.2.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
4	4.3	Organization of mobilization and mutual learning workshops for partners and stakeholders	Methodologies for organization of mobilization and mutual learning workshops for partners and stakeholders	Q-PLAN	All Partners		Methodology for organization of mobilization and mutual learning workshops with the aim to exchange best practices and lessons learned regarding barriers and enablers with respect to policy, regulatory, social, environmental, financial, market and technological dimensions	R 4.3.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

D5.7: Strategic Exploitation Plan - Strategy

4	4.4	Development of the MARINEWIND Action Plan for Public Acceptance of FOWT	MARINEWIND Action Plan for Public Acceptance of FOWT	APRE	All Partners	An action plan aiming to raise citizen's awareness and remove the non-technological barriers for the FOWT access to the market	R 4.4.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
4	4.5	Organisation of webinars	Webinars for policy makers and public authorities	APRE	All Partners	Informative webinars to increase the awareness of policymakers and public authorities for developing more informed RES policy	R 4.5.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
4	4.6	Development of MARINEWIND Replicability Plan	MARINEWIND Replicability Plan	Q-PLAN	All Partners	A dedicated plan including practical guidelines along with lessons learnt, recommendations and tools that will support how to replicate the MARINEWIND experiences in other EU countries non partners	R 4.6.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	Yes	No specific conditions
5	5.1	Development of Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan	Strategic Communication and Dissemination Plan	WavEC	All Partners	A dedicated plan including guidelines for the Consortium regarding all project communication and dissemination activities	R 5.1.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

5	5.2	Set-up of website	MARINEWIND website	WavEC	All Partners	The project's website which will host the project description, the consortium, news and events, information about the project's activities, project's outcomes, information about public policies, market and financial information and the webGIS Tool	R 5.2.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
5	5.3	Set-up of social media channels	MARINEWIND social media channels	WavEC	All Partners	Social media channels to share project's activities, news and information	R 5.3.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
5	5.4	Creation of videos	Videos	WavEC	All Partners	Promotional video plus additional short videos and clips for the website and social media	R 5.4.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions
5	5.5	Networking with other funded projects and initiatives	Methodology for clustering with other projects	APRE	All Partners	A methodology for clustering with relevant projects aiming at maximizing the impact through networking with other EU funded projects	R 5.5.1	Copyright	No specific conditions	No	No specific conditions

5.3 Key Exploitable Results

Table 6: Key Exploitable Results

KER#	Key Exploitable Result	Short description of KER	Main partner(s)	Contributing Partner(s)	Related R number	Related BG number	KER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising concerning M-U-L-S-O (which exploitation path is most promising by the proposed owner)
1	Stakeholder database	A rich database with relevant stakeholders at local (Labs), national and European level and their level of influence in the system	APRE	All partners	R 1.2.1			Copyright		X				U2
2	MARINEWIND webGIS tool	A web multifunctional tool that will provide the stakeholders with tailored information, best practices, financing solutions, guidelines and impact assessments on FOWT	RSE	All partners	R 4.1.1			Not applicable - Open tool		X		X		U2

D5.7: Strategic Exploitation Plan - Strategy

3	Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations	A set of concrete recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders at European and Labs level to ensure the valorization of the activities and results coming from the Labs	Q-PLAN	All partners	R 4.2.1			Copyright	X									U2
4	MARINEWIND Replicability Plan	A dedicated plan compiling all the practical guidelines, lessons learnt, recommendations and tools during the MARINEWIND project to facilitate the uptake of FOWT in other EU countries (non-partners)	Q-PLAN	All partners	R 4.6.1			Copyright	X									U2
5	MARINEWIND brand and community	The MARINEWIND brand and community created and enhanced throughout the duration of the project, facilitating the dissemination and exploitation of the project's assets after its completion	APRE	All partners	All R			Copyright	X									U2

6 EXPLOITATION PLAN PER KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULT

In this section of the Strategic Exploitation Plan the Key Exploitable Results of the MARINEWIND project are described, along with the main contributors to their development. Information is also provided on who their intended users are, the benefits they stand to gain from exploiting that KER as well as on potential exploitation routes. In parallel, the main creator of each KER indicates any foreseeable action that may be needed to facilitate the intended exploitation route(s) of the KER, concisely outlining what needs to be done, when and by whom.

The above information is presented in two tables for each KER:

- One table summarizing the exploitation plan of that KER.
- A second table summarizing any actions needed for the exploitation of that KER.

Each KER is presented in a different sub-section of this section.

The Exploitation Plans per Key Exploitable Result constitute preliminary plans which have been developed according to the current stage of MARINEWIND project and will be updated in the final version of Strategic Exploitation Plan on M36.

6.1 Stakeholder Database

Table 7: Exploitation Plan for the Stakeholder Database

KER Description	A rich database with relevant stakeholders at local (Labs), national and European level and their level of influence in the system
Creators of KER	APRE is the creator of this KER with contribution from all partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MARINEWIND consortium
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the KER	Reference point for stakeholders mapping: the stakeholders database will be a ready tool that all the consortium partners can consult to better understand the engagement level of all the actors in the FOWT context at Labs, European, and extra European level. The database will allow the developing of new possible networks and strengthen the effectiveness of the current networks.
Intended exploitation route	<p>Exploitation path #1: MARINEWIND partners can utilize the MARINEWIND database on other projects, in order to connect it with other partners' databases and strengthen their network of stakeholders relevant to FOWT or to facilitate their project activities.</p> <p>Exploitation path #2: Partners is expected to exploit the database during the MARINEWIND project for targeted communication as whenever newsletters, information or press releases are to be developed concerning the project, it can easily be disseminated to the right and suitable audience. Furthermore, the database will be used to complete MARINEWINDS activities such as workshops, interviews and surveys.</p>

Table 8: Actions needed for the exploitation of the Stakeholder Database

	What?	By whom?	When?
IPR	Copyright	All partners	Once the first version of the database is completed
Validation and fine-tuning	Ongoing process. The database will be updated during the whole project.	All partners	M1 to M36
Communication and dissemination	For internal use and project activities. Available through the consortium's common workspace.	All partners	M1 to M36

6.2 MARINEWIND webGIS tool

Table 9: Exploitation Plan for the MARINEWIND webGIS tool

KER Description	A web multifunctional tool that will provide the stakeholders with tailored information, best practices, financing solutions, guidelines and impact assessments on FOWT
Creators of KER	RSE will create the tool with contribution from all partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the KER	<p>All stakeholders including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia • Regulatory authorities • Civil Society, environmental groups • Policy Makers • Business/Industry, Technology/project providers • SMEs, Investors <p>The tool will be accessible, publicly available and free of charge. The intended user will have access to various information, best practices for applications of FOWT, financing solutions, guidelines about economic impact of FOWT and environmental impact assessments.</p>
Intended exploitation route	<p>Exploitation path #1: Partners will provide free of charge the MARINEWIND webGIS to the public. It is expected to exploit it aiming to attract and engage stakeholders in MARINEWIND project and to disseminate relevant information to local communities.</p> <p>Exploitation path #2: The tool can be further developed after the end of the project or utilized on other research projects and activities which require analysis and elaboration of geo-referenced data on FOWT development.</p>

Table 10: Actions needed for the exploitation of the MARINEWIND webGIS tool

	What?	By whom?	When?
IPR	N/A - Open tool	N/A	N/A
Validation and fine-tuning	For Exploitation Path #1: The tool will be created	#1: All partners	#1: After M6 until M36 #2: After M36

Communication and dissemination	after M6 and fine-tuned during the whole project. For exploitation Path #2: The interested partners will maintain and/or further develop the tool using their own resources	#2: Interested partners	
	The webGIS tool will be publicly available and accessible via the project's website	All partners	Once the tool is launched, after M6

6.3 Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations

Table 11: Exploitation Plan for the Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations

KER Description	A set of concrete recommendations for MARINEWIND stakeholders at European and Labs level to ensure the valorization of the activities and results coming from the Labs
Creators of KER	Q PLAN will create this KER with contribution from all partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the KER	<p>All stakeholders including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia • Regulatory authorities • Civil Society, environmental groups • Policy Makers • Business/Industry, Technology/project providers • SMEs, Investors <p>The MARINEWIND Recommendations is an attractive brochure for the intended users, who can find summarized key outcomes on barriers and enablers with respect to policy, regulatory, social, environmental, financial, market and technological dimensions. Also, the booklet can be useful for FOWT developers to achieve social acceptance, as it is like a kind of “good practices” certification.</p>
Intended exploitation route	The booklet can be exploited as a useful tool to disseminate analyses and project outcomes during and beyond the project in a practical way for a diverse public and for a continuation of the knowledge obtained during the endurance of the project. Also, by giving recommendations partners can facilitate the FOWT market uptake, raise citizens' awareness and aid stakeholders to use the supporting tools and material which are to be developed in the project.

Table 12: Actions needed for the exploitation of the Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations

	What?	By whom?	When?
IPR	Copyright	Q PLAN	End of the project

Communication and dissemination	The booklet will fuel the elaboration of an Action Plan for Public Acceptance of FOWT. Also, it will be publicly available in at least 5 different languages and through the project's website.	All partners	End of the project
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6.4 MARINEWIND Replicability Plan

Table 13: Exploitation Plan for the MARINEWIND Replicability Plan

KER Description	A dedicated plan compiling all the practical guidelines, lessons learnt, recommendations and tools during the MARINEWIND project to facilitate the uptake of FOWT in other EU countries (non-partners)
Creators of KER	Q PLAN will create this KER with contribution from all partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the KER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academia Policy Makers Business/Industry, Technology/project providers <p>The intended users can utilize the Replicability Plan and learn how to replicate the MARINEWIND's experiences in their country.</p>
Intended exploitation route	<p>Exploitation path #1: The Replicability Plan can be exploited as a standalone KER in the form of a practical guideline aiming to support stakeholders relative to FOWT to replicate the knowledge and insights gained during MARINEWIND project.</p> <p>Exploitation path #2: The Replicability Plan can be utilized by partners on other research projects and their activities to support and/or facilitate their successful completion with recommendations and lessons learnt through MARINEWIND.</p>

Table 14: Actions needed for the exploitation of the MARINEWIND Replicability Plan

	What?	By whom?	When?
IPR	Copyright	Q PLAN	M30
Validation and fine-tuning	An initial version of the Replicability Plan will be developed and discussed during a dedicated EU policy virtual roundtable.	All partners	On M30 will be developed and between M30 and M36 will be discussed
Communication and dissemination	The Replicability Plan will be publicly available through the project's website.	All partners	After M30

6.5 MARINEWIND brand and community

Table 15: Exploitation Plan for the MARINEWIND brand and community

KER Description	The MARINEWIND brand and community created and enhanced throughout the duration of the project, facilitating the dissemination and exploitation of the project's assets after its completion
Creators of KER	APRE as the Project Coordinator is the creator of this asset with contribution from all partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the KER	The main target group of MARINEWIND brand and community is all stakeholders involved in the project that can benefit from the project results
Intended exploitation route	The MARINEWIND brand and community represents only the MARINEWIND project. The quality and credibility gained from the effective implementation of the project and its impact can facilitate the engagement of its partners into other EU funded projects and the expansion of their network and client base.

Table 16: Actions needed for the exploitation of the MARINEWIND brand and community.

	What?	By whom?	When?
IPR	Copyright	All partners	M1
Communication and dissemination	The MARINEWIND brand and community will be disseminated and communicated through all the relative activities and material (e.g., leaflets, website, logos etc.)	All partners	From M1 until M36 and beyond the project

7 EXPLOITATION PLAN PER PARTNER

This section summarizes, in tabular format, the Key Exploitable Results of the MARINEWIND project that each partner is currently interested the most to exploit, as well as how they intend to proceed to this end.

Table 17: Individual Exploitation Plans for partners

Individual Exploitation Plans of the MARINEWIND partners	
MARINEWIND partner: APRE	<p>Key Exploitable Results of major interest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder Database • Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations • Replicability Plan • MARINEWIND brand and community
<p>Exploitation Plan: APRE is particularly interested in exploiting MARINEWIND's brand and community as the field's cross-cutting project (Wind Energy and Floating Offshore Wind Technologies sectors) are of strategic interest for APRE, especially from a research perspective. Furthermore, the community to be developed through the stakeholder database will enrich APRE's network of stakeholders relevant to Wind Energy, who are interested in Floating Offshore Wind Technologies, broadening the pool of potential collaborators. Finally, APRE's involvement in the development of MARINEWIND Recommendations and Replicability Plan can enhance its researching methods to better support such actions in other projects.</p>	
MARINEWIND partner: SENER	<p>Key Exploitable Results of major interest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder Database • MARINEWIND webGIS tool • Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations • Replicability Plan
<p>Exploitation Plan: SENER as an engineering and technology group is interested in exploiting the Stakeholders Database to grow its network of business, industry, academia, policy makers and other relevant stakeholders in the Wind Energy domain, especially in the FOWT sector. Also, SENER's involvement in the development of webGIS tool, MARINEWIND's Recommendations and Replicability Plan will strengthen its knowledge portfolio and enable it to provide more efficient testing and validating approaches as well as insights regarding technology state-of-art, social acceptance, and environmental impact analysis.</p>	
MARINEWIND partner: Q PLAN	<p>Key Exploitable Results of major interest:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder Database • Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations • Replicability Plan • MARINEWIND brand and community
<p>Exploitation Plan: Q PLAN is particularly interested in exploiting MARINEWIND's brand and community, as the involvement and continuation in the Renewable Energy Sources and Wind Energy fields are of strategic interest for the organisation, especially from a business perspective. Furthermore, the utilization of stakeholders database will enrich Q PLAN's local and European network of stakeholders interested in Wind Energy and FOWT, broadening the pool of potential clients as well as collaborators. Last but not least, Q PLAN's major role in the development of MARINEWIND Recommendations and Replicability Plan will enhance its expertise and knowledge in the field of FOWT leading to boosting the quality of its services and facilitating the involvement in such EU projects.</p>	

Individual Exploitation Plans of the MARINEWIND partners	
MARINEWIND partner: WavEC	Key Exploitable Results of major interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> MARINEWIND webGIS tool Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations Replicability Plan
<p>Exploitation Plan: WavEC is interested in exploiting MARINEWIND's tool, as well as the Booklet on Recommendations and the Replicability Plan. The contribution of WavEC in the above-mentioned key exploitable results will enrich its knowledge database as well as its expertise in the Marine and FOWT sectors, facilitating the engagement in other EU projects. Furthermore, the involvement in the project will extend WavEC's experience in the preparation of state-of-the-art reports which are focusing on offshore wind technologies, market opportunities, political sceneries and global vision of technological, economic, legal and environmental aspects.</p>	
MARINEWIND partner: CNR	Key Exploitable Results of major interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations Replicability Plan MARINEWIND brand and community
<p>Exploitation Plan: CNR as a Research Institution, is particular interested in exploiting the MARINEWIND's brand as well as the community developed through the project implementation, with the aim to increase its participation in other research projects in the field of FOWT. Furthermore, the involvement in the project's actions along with the contribution to the elaboration of MARINEWIND Recommendations and Replicability Plan will strengthen its expertise in the area of FOWT, but also will enhance its researching methods with new knowledge and data. Utilizing the MARINEWIND Recommendations and Replicability Plan, WavEC can better fulfil its mission to carry out, promote, spread and transfer research in key sectors of knowledge with applications and experiences gained from MARINEWIND project.</p>	
MARINEWIND partner: RSE	Key Exploitable Results of major interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder Database MARINEWIND webGIS tool Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations Replicability Plan MARINEWIND brand and community
<p>Exploitation Plan: RSE will develop the MARINEWIND webGIS tool and is particularly interested in exploiting this multifunctional tool to better analyze and elaborate geo-referenced data on FOWT development. Also, the involvement in the elaboration of MARINEWIND Recommendations and Replicability Plan will enrich its research knowledge and insights, resulting in better support the Italian Ministry of Ecological Transition. Along with that, the exploitation of MARINEWIND brand and community will further extend RSE's network and strengthen its participation in European and International bodies and associations.</p>	
MARINEWIND partner: EP	Key Exploitable Results of major interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder Database Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations
<p>Exploitation Plan: EP is interested in exploiting the Stakeholders Database in order to obtain a better network among the stakeholders involved, which could lead to collaborations, synergies and thus cooperation among all, as well as to be more aware of what is going on among the various stakeholder groups, so increasing the mutual understanding. Furthermore, EP's involvement in the development and exploitation of MARINEWIND Recommendations will strengthen its monitoring and assessing methods as well as its expertise on policy development.</p>	

Individual Exploitation Plans of the MARINEWIND partners	
MARINEWIND partner: UoY	Key Exploitable Results of major interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder Database Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations Replicability Plan
<p>Exploitation Plan: UoY is interested in exploiting the stakeholder database, in order to extend its network of relevant stakeholders who are interested in FOWT, especially those who are part of the academia and business. Furthermore, UoY will utilize the Replicability Plan and the Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations along with the experience gained through MARINEWIND project with the aim to strengthen its researching activities and methods in the FOWT field, especially from the financial scope, and thus to better support the financial and techno-economic analysis and elaboration of results of other research projects.</p>	
MARINEWIND partner: ESC	Key Exploitable Results of major interest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder Database MARINEWIND webGIS tool Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations
<p>Exploitation Plan: ESC is interested in exploiting the stakeholder database aiming to extend its network and facilitate communication between different stakeholders, particularly between technology developers and investors (public and private). Furthermore, ESC's involvement in the development of MARINEWIND webGIS tool and Booklet on MARINEWIND Recommendations will strengthen its knowledge and expertise on policy, regulatory and market design. Also, ESC can exploit the MARINEWIND Recommendations by adapting and implementing them on other innovation applications or can utilize them to encourage system thinking, particularly on whole energy systems, in which their technical team has significant experience and expertise.</p>	

8 CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD

This initial version of the MARINEWIND Strategic Exploitation Plan describes the strategy and methodology employed in this respect within the framework of MARINEWIND, while also providing an overview of its Background and project Results as well its Key Exploitable Results. A dedicated tool, namely the IPR Matrix, has been elaborated to facilitate the identification and management of MARINEWIND's Key Exploitable Results by project partners under the supervision of the Exploitation Manager (Q-PLAN) throughout the project.

Accordingly, the Strategic Exploitation Plan of MARINEWIND will be updated to reflect the final project results along with their protection, ownership, access rights with the support of all partners. The final version of the "Strategic Exploitation Plan" will be elaborated on M36 and provide a more accurate outline of the key exploitable results of the project, the main target groups of external stakeholders (e.g., prospective end-customers) and the potential benefits they stand to gain from MARINEWIND's outcomes, the exploitation plans per key exploitable result and per partner. Additionally, the final report will encompass the measures that have been taken to protect the partnership's IP as well as the respective IPR agreements, fostering the successful post-project exploitation and sustainability of the project's key exploitable results.

The Exploitation Manager is responsible for keeping the Strategic Exploitation Plan updated. In collaboration with all partners, they will monitor project activities as they evolve to timely capture innovation opportunities that may go unnoticed. In parallel, he will identify any potential conflicts of interest and facilitate their resolution before the end of the project, with a view to jointly fostering the smooth post-project exploitation of MARINEWIND results.

9 ANNEX 1 - QUESTIONNAIRE

Organization name: **<Please enter the name of your organization>**

In the following questions on Section 1 and Section 2, please provide us with as much and relevant information as possible. Each question has to be answered for each of the Key Exploitable results that are relevant to your organization (please add lines on the tables below if the existing ones are not enough).

Section 1: Key Exploitable Results

- 1) Which are the KERs, included in the table with the identified exploitable results, which are relevant to your organization? If you identify any further KER that are not included in Table 1, please also provide a brief description of it. What is your organization's role in each relevant KER?

#	Key Exploitable Result	Brief description (Principal characteristics, functions, how it works, etc.)	Role of your organization	
			Main	Contributing
1	<text>	<text if necessary>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	<text>	<text if necessary>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
XXX	<text>	<text if necessary>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- 2) How do you plan on exploiting each of the above-mentioned KER after the end of the project? (for identification of the KER, please use the numbering of the previous table)

KER#	Develop and sell the new product/service	Spin off activity	Cooperation agreement/ Joint venture	Sell IP rights to end users by means of licensing agreements on protected results	Transfer ownership of IP rights to another partner from MARINEWIND consortium by means of licensing agreements and NDA signature.	Standardization activities (new standards or support ongoing procedures)	Utilization on other projects	Other methods. Please indicate
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>

KER#	Develop and sell the new product/service	Spin off activity	Cooperation agreement/ Joint venture	Sell IP rights to end users by means of licensing agreements on protected results	Transfer ownership of IP rights to another partner from MARINEWIND consortium by means of licensing agreements and NDA signature.	Standardization activities (new standards or support ongoing procedures)	Utilization on other projects	Other methods. Please indicate
XXX	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>

3) What makes each KER attractive to the potential markets/users? (Key benefits or problems solved by this new KER? What it does better than similar assets? What it brings to the market?)

KER#

4) Who/which do you think will be the major competitors/ competitive products/solutions for each KER? Can you briefly describe them? (e.g., main characteristics, key strengths, price, etc.)

KER#

5) What would be needed to make each KER ready to be exploitable? (e.g., external financing, obtaining authorization for operation, management structure building, validation of the platform prototype, etc.). Please, separate your answer for during the project and beyond its end.

KER#

6) Are there any legal, normative, or ethical requirements each KER must comply with to enter the target markets?

KER#

7) Which exploitation pathway(s) is more suitable for each KER?

KER#	M: Making a product and selling it	U: Using the project result internally for further development, for instance		L: Licensing the project result to third parties	S: Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc.	Other methods. Please indicate
		U1: to develop something else for sale	U2: for R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research			
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>
xxx	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>

8) What is the value that you would like to get from each KER? (e.g., for scientific, societal, or economic purposes, etc.) And how do you plan to get the value?

KER#

9) Who will be the target customers or users? Who will be interested in each KER? Any potential target customer already shows interests? (e.g., research communities, European policy makers, Industrial companies/innovators, investors, civil society, citizens, etc.)

KER#

Section 2: IPR Strategy and Protection

Background knowledge (existing knowledge, before the start of the project):

a) Does each KER rely on any Background knowledge? What is it and which partner(s) own it?

KER#

b) If each KER is relying on any existing knowledge, how is this background knowledge protected?

ER#	Trade secret	Copy right	Trademark	Patent	Utility model	Other methods. Please indicate	Not protected. Please explain why
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>	<text>				
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>	<text>				
xxx	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>	<text>				

Results (Intellectual protection of the KER):

a) How do you plan to protect each KER?

ER#	Trade secret	Copy right	Trademark	Patent	Utility model	Other methods. Please indicate	Not protected. Please explain why
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>	<text>				
2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>	<text>				
xxx	<input type="checkbox"/>	<text>	<text>				

b) Will any of the KER relevant to your organization be developed by more than one partner?

Yes No

If yes, please indicate the contribution by each partner and how the ownership will be distributed among the partners for each KER that will be developed by more than one partner.

KER#	Partner	Contribution (explain)	Who will own the rights or how right will be shared
##			
##			